

Improved Sayiner Level Crossing ADC

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Abstract — We present simulations showing the primary distortion in a Sayiner level crossing converter is odd harmonic distortion and examine two methods for improving the performance. A cosine-dither technique is presented. The potential benefits of a hybrid delta sigma level crossing converter are discussed.

Nyquist analog-to-digital converters achieve high dynamic range with a large number of quantization levels. Delta sigma oversampling analog-to-digital converters achieve high dynamic range by averaging a large number of coarsely quantized samples together. A zero crossing converter determines the time when the input signal equals a reference signal. A zero crossing converter requires accurate timing to achieve high dynamic range.

By combining a small number of quantization levels with zero crossing times, Sayiner's level crossing converter achieves high dynamic range with a fraction of the complexity of a Nyquist converter and requires less accurate timing than a zero crossing converter.

I. INTRODUCTION

Analog-to-digital conversion may be divided into three categories: (1) parallel or sequential conversion, (2) sampling rate, Nyquist, or oversampling, and (3) amplitude quantization or time quantization (encoding).

Standard Nyquist converters are flash, successive approximation, and pipeline. Flash converters achieve high speed at low resolution with a parallel amplitude quantization algorithm. Successive approximation analog-to-digital converters use a binary step amplitude quantization algorithm for moderate to high resolution at low speed. Pipeline converters break the conversion process down into a series of smaller steps yielding medium resolution at medium to high speeds. Delta-sigma converters are oversampling converters offering high resolution at low speed. Figure 1 compares commercial analog-to-digital converters [1-4].

There has been a renewed interest in ADCs based on time encoding. Time encoding ADCs operate asynchronously. Time encoding papers include: Allier, et al. [5], and Lazar, et al. [6], Høvin [7] and Sayiner [8].

Allier focuses on the low power and small size for use in systems on a chip. Lazar models a loss-free time encoding ADC. Høvin describes a delta sigma frequency-to-digital

converter. Sayiner explains the power and integrated circuit area reductions possible with an asynchronous level crossing ADC.

A continuous time delta-sigma ($\Delta\Sigma$) converter could also be considered a time encoding converter. Delta sigma ADCs trade inexpensive, low tolerance, digital circuits for high tolerance analog circuits. A delta-sigma ADCs high resolution is achieved through digital signal processing. Time encoding converters also trade analog complexity for increased digital signal processing [5-8].

II. LEVEL CROSSING ADC OPERATION

Sayiner [8-11] examines a level crossing converter based on when the input signal's voltage crosses discrete voltage levels of $\Delta, 2\Delta, \dots, (n-1)\Delta, n\Delta$ as shown in Figure 2. Figure 3 compares Sayiner's level crossing converter to a flash analog-to-digital converter. Both converters use the same parallel comparator input structure. A level crossing ADC combines a flash converter's parallel amplitude quantization with the zero crossing times. A second order piece-wise continuous Newton's divided difference interpolator converts the asynchronous level crossings to discrete time. Sayiner's algorithm [11] does not interpolate between zero crossings when the waveform is bounded between two levels. A sine wave's level crossing times for an 8 level, level crossing ADC are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 1 Comparison of ADC Technologies [1-4]

Figure 2 Level Crossing ADC

Figure 3 Comparison of Flash to Level Crossing ADC

Figure 4 Zero Crossing Times

Figure 5 Interpolator Saturation

A. Level Crossing/Encoder Block

The quantization error of a flash converter is bounded by $\pm \frac{1}{2}\Delta$, or half a quantization step. For an ideal resistor ladder (Figure 3), the level crossing converter has zero amplitude quantization error. This is similar to a zero-crossing modulation analog transmission channel. Zero-crossing modulation has zero (amplitude) quantization error [12]. The quantization error for the level crossing ADC is primarily determined by the quantization error in time [8]. The encoder block simply scales the impulse train by the level number.

B. Interpolation

An interpolation stage converts the asynchronous level crossing times from the level crossing detector to discrete time. The filter lengths required for a zero-order hold based sample rate conversion are excessively long [13]. Linear filtering simply ignores the time information in the asynchronous pulse stream [8].

Newton's divided difference interpolation provides good performance for the computation complexity. Sayiner compares the interpolation performance to the order of the interpolator. Even for low orders, the performance quickly approaches saturation. A second order Newton's divided difference polynomial offers a good choice between complexity and performance [8]. At low interpolation orders, the interpolator quickly approaches saturation as shown in Figure 5. We are not checking for a signal bounded between two levels as in Sayiner [11].

The interpolation performance is poor where the input waveform is bounded between two levels. Figure 4 shows the level crossing times for a sine wave input signal. Large gaps in the zero crossing times occur where the slope of the sine wave is near zero. The signal clipping during the large time gaps causes odd harmonic distortion.

Sayiner's level crossing converter model for calculating the signal-to-noise ratio assumes no correlation between amplitude time-pairs. Clearly, this assumption is invalid when the time gaps between pulses become large. For a pure sine wave, the signal-to-noise ratio is worse than calculated by Sayiner; especially for low frequencies where there are more harmonics in a given passband.

A central point interpolator requires a startup time delay to calculate interpolation values near the center point. By delaying the start time by the first two zero crossings at $f = 25$ Hz, the distortion caused by the time delay increases with frequency as shown in Figure 6. The startup time delay should be determined by the highest frequency in the passband. For small time delays, a zero delay giving an endpoint curve fit is a practical solution. Figure 5 shows how the interpolator performance saturates for $f_{clk} = 4.096$ MHz, and $f_{out} = 128$ kHz (interpolator output frequency) for an input of $v_m(t) = 0.8\sin(2000\pi t)$ versus the number of levels and interpolation order.

We study two possible solutions for signal clipping when input signal's slope is near zero or the input signal is bounded between two levels. We examine adding a cosine dither signal to the input signal and secondly, we introduce a new analog-to-digital converter based on a hybrid delta-sigma level crossing ADC. The cosine dither signal places an upper limit on the time delay between zero crossing times in Figure 4 (v_1 and v_2). The delta-sigma level crossing converter increases the number of level crossings and reduces the time between pulses.

C. Decimation (Low Pass Filter)

The level crossing ADCs low pass output filter is a decimation filter typically used in a $\Delta\Sigma$ ADC [14].

III. LEVEL CROSSING ADC SIMULATIONS

Table 1 summarizes two level crossing converter applications [8]. Figure 7 compares harmonic distortion for no interpolation (asynchronous zero-order hold) to parabolic Newton's divided difference interpolation for a 64 level, level crossing ADC.

In Figure 8, a two-tone intermodulation distortion test shows the interpolator glitches when the input signal is bounded between levels. The power spectrum in Figure 9 shows periodic impulse noise. By adding a dither signal, the intermodulation distortion can be improved.

Figure 10 compares the audio application level crossing ADC from Table 1 with and without a 20 kHz cosine dither signal. The dither signal reduces the harmonics by 10 to 20 dB.

Figure 6 Interpolator start up delay

Table 1 Level Crossing Converter Performance [8]

Application	Bandwidth	# of levels	SNR
Speech	4 kHz	64	83.5 dB
Audio	20 kHz	256	93.9 dB

Figure 7 Level Crossing ADC Harmonic Distortion

Figure 10 Single Tone and Cosine Dither

Figure 8 Interpolation Glitches

Figure 11 Two Tone and Cosine Dither

Figure 9 Interpolation Glitch Spectrum

Figure 12 Delta-Sigma Level Crossing ADC

In Figure 11, the audio application level crossing ADC from Table 1 was simulated for a two-tone test signal with and without a 20 kHz cosine dither signal. The two-tone without dither shows a noise floor of about -60 to -75 dBm. The two-tone plus cosine dither shows a remarkable improvement to -103 dBm.

Clearly, a high frequency dither near the top of the passband improves the performance of a level crossing ADC.

IV. DELTA SIGMA LEVEL CROSSING ADC

Figure 12 introduces a hybrid delta sigma level crossing ADC. The delta sigma feedback loop increases the number of

level crossings which reduces the large time gaps near the zero slope regions as shown in Figure 4.

The delta sigma level crossing ADC is an asynchronous feedback loop circuit. The output digital signal can be recovered using a simple decimation filter from a delta sigma ADC. The very high frequency $\Delta\Sigma$ level crossing signal reduces the requirements for having a very long linear filter to recover the digital output signal. We have found that interpolation does not increase the performance of $\Delta\Sigma$ level crossing ADC as shown in Figures 13 and 14. We believe that the $\Delta\Sigma$ level crossing ADC provides an alternative to the level crossing interpolation ADC.

V. CONCLUSION

We have shown that the primary distortion in Sayiner's level crossing converter is odd harmonic distortion caused by clipping the input sine wave. Adding a high frequency cosine-dither signal near the top of the passband improves both single tone and two tone distortion products. We have shown that a hybrid delta-sigma level crossing converter has the potential of working like a delta-sigma converter without using an interpolator as in a level crossing converter.

Figure 13 Comparison of $\Delta\Sigma$ Level Crossing ADCs

Figure 14 Two Tone Comparison of $\Delta\Sigma$ LC ADCs

VI. PUBLICATION

This paper is in the public domain.

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